

InNoWest **Einfach machen!**

Sustainable and digital together in North-West Brandenburg.

Prototyping sustainability - designing sustainable IT

 **Technische Hochschule
Brandenburg**
University of
Applied Sciences

**NACHHALTIGE
DIGITALISIERUNG**

Prototyping Sustainability - designing sustainable IT Agenda

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What you can expect:

- Sustainability, digitalization & IT - why is this important?
- Implementing sustainability in IT - what are some of the current challenges?
- Joint design of sustainable IT - what do sustainable IT products look like?
- Preparation of the presentation
- Presentation of your design results with purchase vote

Survey

- **Objective:** Exploring the possibilities of how consumption of digital devices and services could be made sustainable.
- **Survey:** Determining the status quo
- The survey is completely **anonymous**.
- **Please enter the first letter of your first name, the first letter of your last name and your house number in the Pin field.**
Example: Friederike Lindauer, house number 19 --> FL19
- **Please remember your PIN until the end of the workshop.**
- It takes no more than 10 minutes to complete the survey.
- Answer the questions **honestly** and **independently**. This is the only way we can properly measure the success of our research.

QR code

Sustainability-themed building block ice breaker

- **Goal:** measure your individual IT sustainability footprint
- **What is it all about?**
 - on the basis of your personal use of the smartphone (based on simple questions)
 - an individual IT sustainability footprint (in terms of CO₂, H₂O, working conditions) is measured
 - and materialized by "Lego brick towers"
- **How does it work?**
 - In order to measure an IT sustainability balance sheet, we have prepared 6 stations.
 - They show the impact of daily smartphone use on CO₂ emissions, water consumption and working conditions depending on your user behavior.
- **Stations**
 - CO₂, H₂O, working conditions

The dimensions of sustainability

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Goodland 1995
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.26.110195.000245>

Environmental Sustainability

“ Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. UN World Commission on Environment and Development, 2023 ”

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<https://www.sustain.ucla.edu/what-is-sustainability/>
<https://www.stockholmresilience.org/research/planetary-boundaries/planetary-boundaries-data.html>
<https://earth.org/what-is-sustainability/>

Social Sustainability

“ Description and management of positive and negative effects of systems, processes, organizations and activities on people and social life.

UN Global Compact

”

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814278-3.00004-2>
<https://unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/our-work/social>
<https://www.adecesg.com/resources/faq/what-is-social-sustainability/>

Economic Sustainability - economic viability

“ Economic sustainability goes beyond [increasing the efficiency of production processes and] hoarding wealth by seeking balanced cross-sectoral growth between autonomous sectors in conjunction with continuous modernization of production processes.

(Mendes, 2009)

”

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-443-21942-9.00012-1>

17 Goals for sustainable development

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United Nations an association of **193 countries**
Standing up for **peace, human rights, environmental protection and justice** in the world

Dimensions of sustainability in connection with the SDGs

Planet

Human

Profit

<https://www.oeffentliche-it.de/documents/10181/14412/Wertebasierte+digitalization+for+sustainable+development+in+the+%C3%public+sector>

Information technology (IT) and digitalization

“ **Information technology (IT) in the narrow sense includes all technical resources used to generate, store, archive and use digital information. In a broader sense, this also includes the transmission of information using communication technology.** ”

Gabler Lexicon

“ **By digitalization, we mean the digital conversion and display or implementation of information and communication or the digital modification of instruments, devices and vehicles.** ”

Gabler Lexicon

<https://www.gabler-banklexikon.de/definition/informationstechnologie-it-58827>

<https://cartlyapp.com/de/kann-die-digitalisierung-die-dekarbonisierung-beschleunigen/>

<https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de/definition/digitalisierung-54195#:~:text=The%20term%20of%20digitization%20has%20been%20known%20to%2C%20the%20third%20revolution.>

CO2 footprint of our digital life

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/oekoinstitut/49824684616>

Card-based reflection activity

- **Hardware**
 - Production
 - Use
 - Waste disposal
- **Software**
 - Production
 - Use
 - Waste disposal
- **Content**
- **Working conditions**

Supply chain

The supply chain

<https://www.greenbiz.com/article/child-labor-might-be-hidden-your-smartphones-supply-chain>

Rare earths + precious metals mining

Precious metals

A BREAKDOWN OF THE CRITICAL METALS IN A SMARTPHONE

Some vital metals used to build these devices are considered at risk due to geological scarcity, geopolitical issues or trade policy. This infographic details the critical metals that you carry in your pocket.

ALKALI METAL | ALKALINE EARTH | TRANSITION METAL | BASIC METAL | LANTHANOID

TOUCH SCREEN
It contains a thin layer of **indium** tin oxide, highly conductive and transparent, allowing the screen to function as a touch screen.

49 In
Indium

MICROPHONE, SPEAKERS, VIBRATION UNIT
Nickel is used in the microphone diaphragm (that vibrates in response to sound waves). Alloys containing **neodymium**, **praseodymium** and **gadolinium** are used in the magnets contained in the speaker and microphone. **Neodymium**, **terbium** and **dysprosium** are used in the vibration unit.

28 Ni Nickel
59 Pr Praseodymium
60 Nd Neodymium
64 Gd Gadolinium
65 Tb Terbium
66 Dy Dysprosium

DISPLAY
The display contains several **rare earth elements**. Small quantities are used to produce the colors on the liquid crystal display. Some give the screen its glow.

57 La Lanthanum
59 Pr Praseodymium
63 Eu Europium
64 Gd Gadolinium
65 Tb Terbium
66 Dy Dysprosium

ELECTRONICS
Nickel is used in electrical connections. **Gallium** is used in semiconductors. **Tantalum** is the major component of micro capacitors, used for filtering and frequency tuning.

28 Ni Nickel
31 Ga Gallium
73 Ta Tantalum

CASING
Nickel reduces electromagnetic interference. **Magnesium** alloys are superior at electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding.

12 Mg Magnesium
28 Ni Nickel

BATTERY
The majority of smartphones use **lithium-ion** batteries.

3 Li Lithium
27 Co Cobalt
28 Ni Nickel

Source: University of Birmingham

ELEMENTS
elements.visualcapitalist.com

The Earth's natural resources power our everyday lives. VC Elements breaks down the building blocks of the universe.

We live in a material world.

smartphone composition (weight%)

metal content (weight%)

* (% of total metal value)

(c) BGR/PrinzMayer

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0301420720301392>
<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/08/this-visualization-breaks-down-the-metals-in-a-smartphone/>

World

Dozens missing, 14 dead after illegal gold mine collapses in Venezuela

Miner who survived collapse describes terrifying conditions at the scene

The Associated Press · Posted: Feb 21, 2024 8:29 PM EST | Last Updated: February 22

People gather at the bank of Guacara River Port on Wednesday while waiting for information on the miners.

(Reuters TV/Reuters)

<https://www.cbc.ca/news/world/venezuela-gold-mine-collapse-1.7121916>

Mining of rare earth metals

<https://www.ethicalconsumer.org/technology/global-supply-chain-mobile-phone>

<https://www.dw.com/de/der-kobaltbergbau-im-kongo-wirft-schatten-auf-die-tr%C3%A4ume-von-elektromobilit%C3%A4t/a-41369952>

Material costs

What does the material of a smartphone cost?

Example iPhone 6s

components	price in \$
display / touchscreen / glass	52,50
battery	4,50
Taptic Engine	10,00
mainboard with processor	35,00
storage	22,50
cameras	22,50
other components	84,50
manufacturing	4,50
	236,00 \$ (etwa 209 €)

info. **Bild** Quelle: IHS-Analyse

<https://www.bild.de/digital/smartphone-und-tablet/iphone-6s/was-kostet-das-iphone-6s-plus-42922636.bild.html>

Subsidy

What is a subsidy?

→ In the IT sector, the current focus is on subsidies for chips and semiconductors

<https://www.handelsblatt.com/technik/it-internet/elektronik-abhaengigkeit-von-asien-beunruhigt-deutsche-unternehmen/28948946.html>

How do I know which smartphones are subsidized?

SAMSUNG Galaxy A54 5G 128 GB Awesome Graphite Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
16.31 cm / 6.4 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
128 GB

Betriebssystem
Android 13.0, One UI 5.1, KNOX 3.9

Prozessor
Exynos 1380 (S5E8835)

LVP 489,-

348,74

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei
Bezahle in 12 Raten à 30,57 € (eff. Zins, P.a. 9,9%)**
Gesamtpreis 366,84 €

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

XIAOMI Redmi A2 32 GB Black Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
16.57 cm / 6.52 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
32 GB

Betriebssystem
Android (Go edition)

Prozessor
MediaTek Helio G36

LVP 499,99

79,99

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

APPLE iPhone 13 128 GB Mitternacht Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
15.4 cm / 6.1 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
128 GB

Betriebssystem
iOS 15

Prozessor
A15 Bionic Chip

729,-

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei
Bezahle in 24 Raten à 33,46 € (eff. Zins, P.a. 9,9%)**
Gesamtpreis 803,04 €

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

<https://www.techwalls.com/production-costs-of-smartphones/>

<https://www.investopedia.com/financial-edge/0912/the-cost-of-making-an-iphone.aspx>

Waste

Waste

<https://www.trendingtopics.eu/global-e-waste-monitor-so-viel-elektroschrott-wie-noch-nie/>
<https://www.cbsnews.com/news/the-tragic-cost-of-e-waste-and-new-efforts-to-recycle/>

Production

Production

<https://de.serlo.org/politik/79248/herstellung-eines-smartphones>

<https://www.notebookcheck.com/Xiaomi-Neue-Auftragshersteller-in-Indien-Steigerung-der-Smartphone-Produktion.524475.0.html>

Health

Eye diseases, psychological problems, postural damage, psychological and physical effects on employees

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<https://www.androidauthority.com/owning-smartphone-human-environment-cost-656030/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC775532/>
<https://www.news-medical.net/health/Mental-Health-in-a-Digitalized-Workplace.aspx>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7366948/>
<https://next.ergo.com/en/NWOW/2022/digitalisation-occupational-health-and-safety-OHS-virtual-augmented-reality-VR-AR-Home-Office-remote-video-conferencing-health-wearables.html>
[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/733986/IPOL_STU\(2022\)733986_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/733986/IPOL_STU(2022)733986_EN.pdf)

Data transmission

The evolution of website size

<https://www.greentelligent.website/blog/co2-footprint/>
<https://www.keycdn.com/support/the-growth-of-web-page-size>

Software use, websites

What is the "CO2 weight" of a website?

Minimal Carbon Site 32MB:
<https://karlsruhedigital.minimalcarbon.site>

<https://karlsruhe.digital> 635MB

Reducing the energy consumption of websites:

- using environmentally friendly websites (i.e. with little multimedia content)
- no dynamic content, such as videos on autoplay or dynamic web fonts

<https://www.greentelligent.website/blog/co2-footprint/>

Content moderation

Content moderation in social media

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Work leads to:

- Trauma → since all possible cases are seen (sexual abuse of children, rape, torture, bestiality, beheadings, suicide and murder)
- Worldwide distribution of the work due to different languages and cheap labor in other countries
- The work experience of the content moderators is not transferable to other fields of work → a change is almost impossible

<https://www.theverge.com/2019/6/19/18681845/facebook-moderator-interviews-video-trauma-ptsd-cognizant-tampa>
<https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-42920554>
<https://www.cnet.com/tech/tech-industry/facebook-content-moderators-are-suffering-from-ptsd-claims-lawsuit/>
<https://restofworld.org/2024/content-moderators-jobs-pakistan/>

Fake news

Quelle: Facebook, <https://bit.ly/3yIXd9I> [Screenshot am 13.07.2021 | Education Innovation Lab], Bildnachweis/ Foto: Arbeitsvorlagen A5

21. August 2016 · 14 · 8 Kommentare · 23 Mal geteilt

Kirche in München, sechs Neubürger urinieren an das christliche Gotteshaus. TEILEN das auch der letzte Gutmensch diese Sauerei mitbekommt. Respektlos und traurig, bin sprachlos. Stellt euch vor was die mit uns machen würden wenn wir selbiges an einer Moschee tun ?

14 · 8 Kommentare · 23 Mal geteilt

Gefällt mir · Kommentieren · Teilen

Relevanteste zuerst

Nach der Tradition der orthodoxen Christen in Eritrea und Äthiopien gehen die Gläubigen oft nicht in die Kirche hinein, sondern beten draußen vor der Kirche. Sie lehnen sich an die Wand des Gotteshauses und beten. Die Männer auf diesem Bild beten gera... **Mehr ansehen**

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 1 J.

1 Antwort

Die Männer pinkeln nicht, sie beten.

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 4 J.

Ich habe Anstand und Respekt gelernt, aber keinen "Menschen" gegenüber, die es unserer Kultur nicht entgegenbringen.

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 4 J.

Church desecration or fake news?

<https://www.bpb.de/kurz-knapp/lexika/das-junge-politik-lexikon/320271/fake-news/>
https://www.boell.de/sites/default/files/2021-09/Selbstbestimmt_im_Netz_Fake_News_02_Anhang.pdf

Search engine

What makes a search engine sustainable?

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Hosting

- Co2 neutral
- Based on renewable energies (solar, hydropower)

Profits

- Are donated to innovative, social & charitable causes
- Are invested in environmental protection
- Planting of trees

Data protection

- No collection of user data
- Encryption of search queries
- No cookies, no tracking tools
- Anonymous search

ECOSIA

GOOD

ekoru

lilo

<https://zeit---geist.de/magazin/nachhaltige-gruene-suchmaschinen/>

Click Worker

Click Worker

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taskrabbit

Services Sign up / Log in Become a Tasker

Assembly service provided for
IKEA

Book trusted help for home tasks

What do you need help with?

Assembly Mounting Moving Cleaning Outdoor Help Home Repairs Painting Trending

General Furniture Assembly IKEA Assembly Crib Assembly PAX Assembly Bookshelf Assembly Desk Assembly

Typical „Task Rabbit“ tasks in app usage are:

- Tagging
- Product descriptions
- Translations
- ...

<https://www.taskrabbit.com/>

Cloud

What is a cloud?

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Router

Modem

Internet provider

Data is being stored in the cloud.

Data/data centers

Network cable

<https://coolinfographics.com/blog/2016/4/11/what-are-data-centers.html>

How are data centers related to sustainability?

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<https://dallasinnovates.com/compass-datacenters-and-schneider-electric-partner-in-red-oak-to-build-prefab-data-center-infrastructure/>
<https://www.simslifecycle.com/infographics/data-centers/>

3 GOOD HEALTH
AND WELL-BEING

Doom Scrolling

7 AFFORDABLE AND
CLEAN ENERGY

6 CLEAN WATER
AND SANITATION

12 RESPONSIBLE
CONSUMPTION
AND PRODUCTION

What is doom scrolling and how does it relate to sustainability?

Doom scrolling not only has an impact on your psyche but also consumes...

233.38 gram CO2

28.15 liters of water

2187.9 mAh

= is a phenomenon of constantly scrolling or surfing through social media and the like to keep up to date with the latest news (and especially bad news)

With an average Internet use of 204 minutes per day.

<https://hsb-akademie.de/doomscrolling-problem-der-digitalisierten-neuzeit-und-wie-sie-es-ueberwinden/>
<https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/168069/umfrage/taegliche-internetnutzung-durch-jugendliche/>

AI assistant

The anatomy of a voice assistant

<https://www.theverge.com/2018/9/9/17832124/ai-artificial-intelligence-supply-chain-anatomy-of-ai-kate-crawford-interview>

What does an AI assistant have to do with sustainability?

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AI WATER FOOTPRINT

The researchers noted that for a simple conversation of roughly 20-50 questions and answers

ChatGPT needs to "drink"

A 500 ML BOTTLE OF WATER

Researchers warn that the figures may multiply several times over for the recently launched GPT-4 AI system, which boasts a larger model size.

The paper is yet to be peer reviewed

NEWS 18
creative

<https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/photos/technology/thirsty-ai-chatgpt-drinks-staggering-amount-of-water-to-answer-50-questions-10442101-2.html>

Influencer Economy

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

Influencer economy - blessing or curse?

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<https://omr.com/de/daily/creator-economy>

<https://www.theguardian.com/fashion/2022/feb/24/hustle-and-hype-the-truth-about-the-influencer-economy>

Guiding principles of sustainable IT

Reusability

Avoidance of negative effects

Preservation of resources

Efficiency of data transmission

Efficiency of data storage

Health and accessibility

Time for a short
BREAK!

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Sustainability and smartphone

- Smartphones can be made more sustainable at every stage of the supply chain
- Key words
 - Working conditions
 - Rare earths and precious metals
 - Design

Sustainability and smartphone

- What does the sustainability of a smartphone depend on?
 - Pay attention to natural resources with fair or certified extraction
 - Pay attention to working conditions when extracting resources and in production
 - Pay attention to an easily repairable design
 - Design the product for longevity
 - Remove superfluous product details, e.g. one camera instead of three

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**Modular design =
repairable design**

Sustainability and smartphone

What does the sustainability of a smartphone depend on?

- Ensure climate-friendly transportation
- Choose climate-friendly packaging, e.g. no plastic
- Offer a low-cost repair service
- Provide updates for the smartphone for a long time

Sustainability and smartphone

What does the sustainability of a smartphone depend on?

- Offer recycling program for customers
- Buy up old appliances
- Dispose of old appliances correctly

**Turn the device you have
into the one you want.**

<https://medium.com/macoclock/experience-of-trade-in-apple-iphone-6a52f79a8b68>

How do I make my website more sustainable?

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1. Fewer images or lower resolution

2. Videos not on autoplay

3. As little advertising, tracking & cookies as possible

4. Where possible, avoidance of dynamic content (photo carousel etc.)

5. Use system fonts

- If there are a lot of elements on the page, the likelihood of a service or product being purchased decreases:
<https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/marketing-strategies/app-and-mobile/mobile-page-speed-new-industry-benchmarks-elements-reduce-conversion/>

As the number of elements — text, titles, images — on a page goes from 400 to 6,000, the probability of conversion drops 95%.

Google/SOASTA Research, 2017.

Sustainability and app

- Apps consume energy during:
 - App storage on server
 - Data transmission
 - Data usage
- Less stored content = more sustainable design

Server in a data center

Data transmission

Data usage over app

Sustainability and app

- Sustainable app design is simple
- True to the motto: “All you need is less”
- This means that fewer functions and less data in the app are more sustainable

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https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hans-Knud-Arndt/publication/279141699_Impact_of_Design_on_the_Sustainability_of_Mobile_Applications/links/55b89fba08aec0e5f439b234/Impact-of-Design-on-the-Sustainability-of-Mobile-Applications.pdf
<https://uxstudioteam.com/ux-blog/reduce-digital-carbon-footprint-through-ux-design/>

How can I design an app more sustainably?

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1. Hosting the server with providers that use 100% renewable energy

2. Reduce resolution of videos, images & avoid AI-generated content

3. Include as few app messages as possible

4. Use night mode where possible - this requires less energy

5. Optimize the app for as few clicks as possible

Design Thinking Motivation

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"More than 80% of a product's environmental impact is already determined in the design phase".

Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions.
["A New Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe."](#) *European Commission, 2020 (PDF)*

What can you expect today?

1. Learn about sustainable IT design

2. Get to know your product and customer

3. Become a sustainability designer

Product development- prototyping

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Define persona (customer)

Helps you to understand the needs of your customers.

- Goals
- Motivation
- Frustration
- General description
- Favorite brands

Test and adapt: Check for sustainability

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- ✓ Product is designed to fulfill its purpose
 - ✓ Requirements of the persona were recorded and implemented in the prototype
- => Can these requirements be implemented even more sustainably and will the product still fulfill its purpose?

- **Maria wants a smartphone for her tutoring influencer activities**
- Maria doesn't like cell phones that you can't hold with one hand
- **Design idea: Mobile phone should be easy to hold with one hand - adjust dimensions? Insert holder?**
- Maria would like to use software for learning: e.g. quizzes
- **→ Design Idea: tutoring software should be pre-installed on the cell phone**
- Maria is a fan of the Leica brand
- **→ Design Idea: The cell phone has a good camera from Leica built in**

Mock-up per product

A mock-up is a sketch or a painted design with lettering.

Here on the left are the design ideas for Maria's smartphone in a design processed with inscriptions.

What is next?

Decide on a product:

- Smartphone
- Website
- App

Work on task 1:

- How should the product be designed?
- What content/features should the product have?
- What content/characteristics are added by the persona?

Work on task 2:

- Realize contents and features of the product in a paper design
- => Design prototype

Work on task 3:

- Check whether the content or properties of the product can be implemented more sustainably
- Customize prototype

Work on task 4:

- Develop presentation

Smartphone	Website	App

Task I - Finding ideas

- Developing design ideas: What should the product look like? (Color scheme, design, content, (no-)gos, etc.)
- Write these down
- Develop ideas for 7 or more statements about your persona
- Which features need to be added to the product so that the needs of the persona can be met?

Task III - Check prototype for sustainability

- Take a look at the features of the product or implementation of the content and requirements in your paper design.
- How can implementation be made more sustainable?
- Tip1: Go through the supply and production chain of the product up to the application.
- Tip 2: Get the sustainability catalog.
- Adjust your mock-up accordingly.

1. Hosting the server with providers that use 100% renewable energy

2. Reduce resolution of videos, images & avoid AI-generated content

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5. Optimize the app for as few clicks as possible

1. Fewer images or lower resolution

2. Videos not on autoplay

3. As little advertising, tracking & cookies as possible

4. Where possible, avoidance of dynamic content (photo carousel etc.)

5. Use system fonts

Task IV - Prepare presentation

Fill out the presentation template

Prepare your paper design for presentation

- Which sustainability principles have you implemented?
- Why?
- How does your product differ from comparable products on the market?

Preparing a survey for your classmates:

- Would your classmates buy the product?
 - Why yes?
 - Why not?
- Collect the answers and decide how they can influence the product you have designed

Lunch break
until 12:30

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Checklist for the presentation

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- 7 statements of the persona are transformed into design ideas.
- The statements are marked and labeled on the paper design.
- 4 of the design ideas support sustainability and are marked accordingly on the paper design.
- The presentation template is completed.
- The mock-up is ready for presentation.
- The presentation content is divided between the group members.

→ 3 min presentation + short feedback

Each of you is part of the jury.
--> Jury Worksheet

Presentations

Group 1 - Smartphone

Group 2 - Smartphone

Group 1 - App

Group 2 - App

Group 1 - Website

Group 2 - Website

Do you remember the survey at the beginning of the workshop ...

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- Please do not forget to **enter the PIN** again.
- **Please enter the first letter of your first name, the first letter of your last name and your house number in the Pin field.**
Example: Friederike Lindauer, house number 19 --> FL19
- Answer the questions **honestly** and **independently**. This is the only way we can properly measure the success of our research.
- **We are looking forward to the answers!**

QR code

Award ceremony

- Award for best-selling product
- Award for the most sustainable product

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olga.levina@th-brandenburg.de

Thank you for your participation!

Backup materials